

SURVIVING THE SHIFT: ACADEMIC ADJUSTMENTS AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TRANSFER STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to determine how senior high school transferees adjust academically as they bring their experiences to the St. Louis School of Don Bosco Dumaguete. The study utilized a phenomenological study to discover and interpret the lived experiences of the senior high school transferees of St. Louis School of Don Bosco regarding academic adjustments. This study utilized a purposive sampling design. The data were collected through interviews and were analyzed using the Colaizzi's method of data analysis. The participants in the study were purposely selected based on the inclusion criteria: the respondents are transferees officially enrolled in St. Louis School of Don Bosco, they are from the senior high school department, and they are not returning students. The research instrument utilized in the study was the interview questionnaire or guide which contains questions about the experiences of senior high transferees in terms of academic adjustments. The academic and social support from these relationships played a significant role in easing their transition and helping them adapt more effectively. Overall, the study highlighted the diverse experiences of transfer students, emphasizing their academic challenges and the strategies they used to cope. These findings underscore the crucial role of peer support in facilitating a smoother transition for students.

Keywords: *Academic Adjustments; Senior High School; Transfer Students*

INTRODUCTION

The shift from junior high to senior high school is a prevailing phenomenon that notably impacts students' academic and social experiences, especially for transfer students. They encounter several problems when transferring to a new institution, which can cause culture shock owing to unfamiliar environments and social dynamics, to adjust to the differences in academic rigor, campus size, and school culture (Bouquia et al., 2023). Furthermore, their frequent anxiety is associated with concerns about academics, financial demands, campus connections, and self-esteem - all of which might hinder their adjustment process. Conducting this study addresses the concerns and experiences of senior high transfer students in St. Louis School of Don Bosco, Inc. With the help of this research, the school can delve more into the concerns and struggles they face.

School transitions and student mobility are significant areas of concern in education research due to the enormous influence changing schools can have on students' academic performance, mental wellbeing, and overall academic participation (OECD, 2021). When students change schools, they struggle with variations in the curriculum, leading to learning gaps that negatively influence their academic performance (National Student Clearinghouse Research Center, 2023).

Moreover, social adjustment problems happen since transferees must adapt to a new social group, which causes stress and anxiety (Reyes & Dizon, 2022). Such difficulties of learning continuity have been linked to low academic motivation and lower achievement rates for transferees (DepEd, 2023). Similarly, a report indicated in the United States that only 33.7% of students transferring from a two-year institution earned a bachelor's degree in six years, mirroring overall issues of academic persistence and transfer between institutions (National Student Clearinghouse Research Center, 2022).

In the Philippines, student transfers have been progressively frequent, especially within the senior high school department. The Department of Education noted that in 2023 there are 15% of senior high school students transferred schools, citing main reasons such as environmental adjustment, institutional incompatibilities, and economic difficulties (DepEd, 2023). A study by Reyes and Dizon (2022) also revealed a decline in academic performance upon transfer of the 40% of the nation's senior high school transferees, whereas the majority struggled accepting new academic expectations and social adjustment.

These findings bring to light the significance of examining how transferees cope with new learning environments, the difficulties that they encounter, and the methods they employ in coping with these challenges. All these are essential in the design of specific interventions that can allow senior high school transferees all over the country to excel academically as well as remain psychologically sound.

Ultimately, in this study, the researchers expect that by the end of the conducted research, they can recommend strategies to aid transfer students. They seek to provide data and documentation that can help the researchers and the community. Through this

study, institutions may have this as a foundation to properly accommodate transfer students, enabling them to manage their academic, social, and mental concerns.

Research Objectives

The study aimed to discover the lived experiences of the transfer students in their new academic environment. It sought to understand the academic adjustments the transfer students deal with in moving from one environment to another.

METHODOLOGY

Participants and Site of Study

The participants in the study were purposely selected based on the inclusion criteria: the respondents are transfer students enrolled in St. Louis School of Don Bosco; they are from the senior high school department; and they are not returning students. The study utilized purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling in which respondents are purposefully chosen based on certain qualities that match the study's criteria (Palinkas et al., 2015). The purposive sampling technique used in the present study not only helped ensure the selection of appropriate participants but also attempted to obtain rich qualitative data that would yield a more in-depth understanding of the experiences and views of transferees in the educational context.

Research Design

Phenomenological research is a qualitative approach that centers on the experiences of people who have firsthand knowledge of a phenomenon (Creswell & Poth, 2018). In contrast, descriptive research aims to provide a thorough grasp of a subject by studying and classifying characteristics (Singh, 2023). Both approaches are useful for examining how STEM students deal with setbacks and stay motivated, which may challenge preconceived notions.

Research Instrument

The research instrument utilized in the study was the interview questionnaire or guide which contains questions about the experiences of senior high transferees from St. Louis School of Don Bosco in terms of academic adjustments. The interview was deemed significant because their responses served as our source of information in understanding their academic adjustments.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers submitted an official letter signed by the research adviser, recognized by the senior high coordinator, and approved by the principal to conduct interviews with the selected individuals. The letter was delivered to the individuals

involved. The study's goal and purpose were outlined first. The researchers also explained the advantages of participation in the specified activity.

Upon receiving the letter, the researchers conducted the interviews, which were recorded with permission from the interviewees. Questions about the personal experiences of senior high transferees of them adjusting to the academics of Saint Louis School of Don Bosco will be asked. The interview will last for 10-15 minutes. After gathering the data from different interviews and records, the analysis and interpretations of the data will be made.

Data Analysis

This research study made use of Colaizzi's phenomenological methodology to guarantee and ensure the trustworthiness of information needed in the research including the emotional congruence concerning the lived experience of each participant's point of view. Moreover, it utilized the descriptive approach to gain a comprehensive understanding of the relationships among variables and use it to produce generalizations. The researchers collaborated in transcribing the gathered information. After transcription, the leader reviewed the recordings to correct any errors. Each interview was carefully analyzed to capture unique perspectives, enabling the researchers to fully grasp the essence of participants' experiences. Significant statements and formulated meanings were drafted, and emergent themes were framed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Academic Struggles Faced Upon Entering New Institutions

Through the interview and the further investigations, it was revealed that many participants struggled academically upon transferring to SLSDB. The participants similarly showed that they struggled due to how their lessons were being taught and their major subjects being a stumbling block. Additionally, a gap was identified between their previous school and current school with their grades. These struggles align with the findings from previous studies, which also highlighted the challenges that transfer students face when adjusting to a new academic environment. A study by Filomena and Maravilla (2020) found that the senior high school students in a Catholic school in Antique were experiencing a hard transition problem. This is caused by their preference to apply active coping mechanisms when dealing with problems.

Similarly, Acosta (2020) examined the adjustment experiences and struggles that transferees face regarding academic struggles, non-academic involvement, and ethnicity. These factors made it difficult for these students to adapt and integrate into the school environment. In line with these findings, El Jerdi's (2023) research established that transfer students face several challenges, including academic, financial, and personal obstacles. These difficulties hinder their performance during the transition to a new

school. Additionally, students may feel burdened by the stark differences between their previous and current institutions (Chan et al., 2021).

Peer Assistance in School Work

Peer assistance plays a crucial role in helping transferee students navigate academic challenges, providing both emotional and educational support during their transition. Bouquia et al. (2023) emphasized that transfer students often struggle with adjusting to new academic expectations, school culture, and social integration. However, peer support can ease these difficulties by offering guidance and fostering a sense of belonging. This is evident among the participants. They adjusted well due to assistance from a classmate and the connections formed during summer clinics. These connections likely provided both social and academic support, making the transition smoother. Similarly, they noted that feeling welcomed and supported by peers made the adjustment process more comfortable. This concurs with Latorre-Coscolluela et al. (2022), who found that social reinforcement positively impacts students' motivation and engagement in academic tasks.

Beyond easing the transition, peer support also encourages academic persistence. They acknowledged putting significant effort into academics but still credited peers for their help, Romano et al. (2021) revealed that academic resilience is strengthened through external support systems. Likewise, the participants highlighted the importance of both academic effort and maintaining relationships with classmates, reinforcing Turnquest et al.'s (2023) argument that positive peer interactions enhance motivation and learning strategies. Moreover, forming peer connections is not just beneficial but necessary for academic success, where a respondent advised fellow transferees not to be reserved, emphasizing that friendships provide essential academic assistance. Adorna (2022) supported this claim by asserting that students who perceive their school environment as welcoming and inclusive exhibit greater motivation and academic engagement.

Overall, the experiences of transfer students demonstrate that peer support significantly impacts their academic adaptation, reinforcing existing research on the importance of social integration in learning. Studies suggest that without such support, transferees may experience heightened stress and lower motivation, ultimately affecting their performance (Bouquia et al., 2023; Turnquest et al., 2023). By fostering strong peer connections, schools can create an environment where transferee students feel supported both academically and emotionally, enhancing their overall academic success.

Marked Improvements in Academic Performance

The current findings reveal that a group of the transferees that found they were more comfortable in adjusting to the new institution than the rest. These transferees manifested improvements in their academic performance that can be linked to multiple research findings. One example comes from a study by Adorna (2022) conducted on transferee students in Misamis University. It investigated the engagement and success-

driven goals of the students. The results revealed that the transfer students exhibited exceptional involvement and set ambitious goals. Their academic performance was remarkably stronger (Adorna, 2022). In another instance, Tus (2020) conducted a study to examine the relationships between student stress, motivation, and academic performance. In one of the respondents, they mentioned their coping mechanism to stay in line with academics is to ensure full attention in class discussions to lower the time needed for studying. This correlates with the study that students who had lower levels of stress used coping techniques, such as problem-solving and time management. While students who used emotional coping techniques, such as avoidance and venting, were more likely to experience academic stress.

Despite these variances in coping mechanisms, students' overall academic achievement was generally rated satisfactory or very satisfactory. During the interview, the respondents' experiences with their academic progress were similar. They mentioned how they showed improvements and how glad they were with their academic results due to the environment they were in. The findings from the interview can be linked with the results of the study of Dela Cruz et al. (2021). School readjustment significantly and favorably affects their social exposure and raises their academic performance. One of the statements from the participants shared how they felt pressured due to its competitive environment which drove them to improve. From their statement, it relates to how emotions play a vital role in transfer students' experiences, giving institutions the chance to enhance their students' learning results (Turnquest et al., 2021). The overall results from the different studies point to the complex factors affecting academic performance and adjustment of students.

Conclusions

The study revealed profound insights about their experiences as transfer students. The participants experienced academic challenges when adjusting to the new institution. Some performed better academically before transferring, while others showed improvement after the transition. However, their experiences varied depending on their previous school environment and personal characteristics, which influenced how they adapted. The main difficulties they faced centered on academic performance and social interactions. Challenges included adjusting to a different school culture, adapting to new policies and rules, and integrating into a social environment where peers were already familiar with one another.

To overcome these challenges, students adopted various adjustment strategies. A common approach was seeking support and assistance from their peers. The academic and social support from these relationships played a significant role in easing their transition and helping them adapt more effectively. Overall, the study highlighted the diverse experiences of transfer students, emphasizing their academic challenges and the strategies they used to cope. These findings underscore the crucial role of peer support in facilitating a smoother transition for students.

Recommendations

Transfer students are encouraged to take an active role in their transition by maintaining a positive and open mindset toward change. Since experiences vary depending on personal characteristics and previous school environments, students should recognize that adjustment is a gradual process. Being patient with oneself and understanding that academic and social adaptation takes time can reduce stress and build resilience during the transition period. On the other hand, teachers are also encouraged to promote structured peer-support systems within their classes. Assigning peer buddies, forming mixed-group activities, and fostering collaborative learning environments can ease social integration. Since peer support was identified as a crucial coping strategy, educators play an important role in facilitating meaningful student interactions that enhance both academic engagement and social belonging.

For future researchers, it is recommended to explore additional variables that may influence transfer students' adjustment, such as family support, socio-economic background, mental health factors, and digital or online learning environments. Longitudinal studies examining long-term academic performance and social development after transferring would also provide deeper insights. Further research may also investigate the effectiveness of peer-mentoring programs and institutional interventions in improving both academic outcomes and overall well-being among transfer students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research paper adheres to ethical considerations that contain multiple principles to maintain the protection of the participants. The student researchers upheld integrity and complete honesty in the gathering, processing, and reporting of data to guarantee that the results of the study correspond to the truth. Participants were treated equally, free from prejudice or discrimination, with their rights fully respected throughout the study. Confidentiality was maintained by safeguarding participants' personal information. The research followed the guidelines of informed consent, which involved providing the student participants with detailed information regarding the objectives, processes, possible risks, and advantages of the study. This guaranteed that every participant chose to take part willingly and with full understanding, along with the assurance that their involvement was completely optional and that they could opt to back out at any moment without facing any repercussions.

No conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Furthermore, plagiarism was strictly and firmly avoided and respect for intellectual property was highly achieved. There was no prejudice in the analysis of the results and that, the findings were used purely for research.

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